

ЗРУЧНИЙ КОМПЛЕКСНИЙ МЕТОД ОЦІНКИ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК КОЛОРЕКТАЛЬНОГО АНАСТОМОЗУ

A COMFORTABLE COMBINED WAY OF ASSESSMENT OF COLORECTAL ANASTOMOSIS

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Introduction: Colorectal anastomosis failure after rectal or sigmoid resection is still a problem in colorectal surgery, and its frequency remains stable through the years. This complication increases postoperative mortality and rehospitalization rate. Existing decisions and proposed new methods to solve these problems like ICG either do not fully do the job or do not have a world-known scale of assessment and have very expensive equipment. Mortality from anastomotic leaks reaches 18.00 % (Wang C.B., et al.).

Objective: to investigate the results of visual assessment of colorectal anastomosis (CA) with the implementation of a scoring system for laparoscopic resection of the sigmoid colon.

Materials and methods: results of the treatment of 70 patients who had undergone resections of the sigmoid colon for cancer were analyzed. The patients were divided into two groups. The first group consisted of 35 (50.00 %) patients, whose treatment method was laparoscopic resection of the sigmoid colon with stapler anastomosis and a combined visual assessment was applied (main group). The second group consisted of 35 (50.00 %) patients who underwent the same operation but only a leak test was performed. The visual assessment of the anastomosis was performed taking into account both external and internal characteristics. For the external assessment, visual assessment and pneumohydrostatic probe were used, for the internal – an ordinary 10 mm laparoscope was inserted into the anus with CO₂ insufflation at the level of 6 mm Hg. During an intracorporeal assessment of the anastomosis and using videorectoscopy supplier defects, bleedings, and ischemic zones were searched.

Results. Specific complications were observed in 5 (14.28 %) patients of the main group during the surgery. There were some of them: visualized stapler brackets,

submucosal hematoma, and pale mucosa color. These complications were eliminated using an additional reinforcement suture line with separated Vicryl 2/0 sutures. No anastomotic leak in the main group in the postoperative period was observed. In the second group 3 patients (8.57 %) had anastomosis failure in the first week after the operation. These cases required reoperation with the removal of the anastomosis and formation of terminal colostomy. No lethal cases were in both group. Using additional methods for assessing anastomosis was time-consuming but efficient in patients with an increased risk of anastomotic leak ($p < 0.05$). The developed technique for assessing the anastomosis made it possible to improve the total results of the treatment.

Conclusions. Prevention of colorectal anastomosis leaks remains an unresolved problem. It is necessary to further identify strong points of the proposed method of combined visual assessment of colorectal anastomosis and the ways to prevent colorectal anastomosis leak in order to get rid of protective ileostomy necessity.

Keywords: colorectal anastomosis, laparoscopic resection, anastomosis failure, anastomosis reinforcement, anastomosis assessment.